

Politically Misleading Large Language Models: Evidence from the 2024 U.S. Presidential Elections Reveals LLM Fact-Checking Limitations

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1. Introduction

While Large Language Models (LLMs) with web search capabilities are increasingly used to verify information, their reliability for political fact-checking remains questionable. We present a comprehensive evaluation of seven state-of-the-art LLMs on their ability to fact-check political statements related to the 2024 U.S. presidential election. Using a dataset of 1,374 statements derived from 530 original claims fact-checked by major organizations in the run-up to the elections, we test both original and reformulated versions of statements. Our findings reveal that even the best-performing models achieve only modest accuracy (macro F1 score of 0.51), with web search providing minimal improvements over models without search capabilities. Models particularly struggle with nuanced “misleading” statements and demonstrate poor robustness to reformulations. These results indicate that users relying on LLMs for political fact-checking are likely to receive inconsistent and sometimes incorrect assessments, even for statements that have been previously fact-checked by professional organizations and are readily available online.

